

Multiphysics Study of Plating Phenomena in the Lotus Molten Chloride Reactor Integrating Neutronics, Thermohydraulics, and Thermochemistry

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804038

ABSTRACT

Plating and chemical species tracking capabilities are pressing needs for understanding and development of molten salt reactors. This study presents preliminary results from a multiphysics simulation of the Lotus Molten Chloride Reactor, incorporating neutronics, thermohydraulics, and thermochemical equilibrium solvers to study the plating phenomena of the NaCl-UCl₃ binary eutectic system under steady-state conditions at 25 kW of thermal power. The simulations were performed using a Griffin-Pronghorn-Thermochemica multiphysics model on the Idaho National Laboratory (INL) High-Performance Computing (HPC) resources. Preliminary results indicate a strong dependence of plating phenomena on temperature and elemental composition of the salt. Further work should aim to verify the model and validate the results using experimental setups such as the Molten Salt Test Loop.

Keywords: Plating, Molten Salt, Multiphysics, Lotus Reactor, NaCl-UCl₃

1. INTRODUCTION

The Molten Chloride Fast Reactor (MCFR) is an advanced conceptual design of a fast reactor that makes use of a molten salt fuel mixture composed of sodium and uranium chlorides. Studies and experiments such as the Molten Chloride Reactor Experiment (MCRE) play a key role in improving the understanding of the physics, safety, and performance of these new technologies [1]. This type of reactor offers several advantages, including higher operating temperatures, lower operating pressures, and better fuel utilization. However, electrochemical phenomena, precipitation and plating of fission products, and the chemical effects associated with fission product buildup remain important topics for the continued development of this type of technology.

MCRE is a research project aimed at improving the understanding of molten salt reactor technology. This joint initiative between Idaho National Laboratory (INL), TerraPower, and Southern Company is expected to begin operation in 2028 and run for approximately 18 months to collect experimental data. The LOTUS Molten Chloride Reactor (LMCR) is an open-source, generic chloride fuel-salt reactor model derived from the MCRE. It was developed by INL to further advance research on advanced nuclear reactors through modeling and simulation within the Virtual Test Bed (VTB) repository.

The introduction of an additional thermochemical solver within neutronic/thermo-hydraulic solvers is motivated by recent research on isotopic evolution in molten salt reactors and the need to further study corrosion dynamics and track fuel salt behavior during operation [2]. The present study aims to present a model for material deposition on surfaces (plating) for the open-source LOTUS model, to which we refer to as LMCR. In which the element of interest is chromium (Cr); however, the approach can be extended to other elements. This preliminary model establishes the temporal relationships among dissolved species, solid species in suspension, colloids, and solid species plated on the system surfaces.

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2. METHODOLOGY

For the development of the multiphysics model, MOOSE-based (Multiphysics Object Oriented Simulation Environment) applications were employed to couple the different physical phenomena involved. In this case, Griffin provided reactor physics capabilities, Pronghorn solved Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) equations through a k-epsilon model, and Thermochemica computed the equilibrium concentrations of the system phases through Gibbs energy minimization problem [3].

2.1. Model Description

The three-dimensional mesh of the LMCR model was generated based on the MCRE Reactor Enclosure System [4]. Several assumptions were made to simplify the geometry, including the removal of the drain pipe, the omission of the core impingement structure, and the relocation of the pump. Figure 1a displays the reactor enclosure system of MCRE, while Figures 1b, 1c, and 1d provide insight of the mesh utilized.

Figure 1. Overview of MCRE reactor enclosure system and LMCR mesh
 Legend: ■ Core, ■ Pump, ■ Pipe, ■ Reflector

2.2. Governing Equations

Multiple governing equations were established to model the expected physics of the system. Each code solved a different component of the simulation, employing distinct equations and discretization methods. For the neutronics component, the Griffin code solved a nine-group multigroup diffusion equation to obtain the power density and fission source terms [5]. Additionally, considerations were taken to incorporate the effects of advection and diffusion of delayed neutron precursors on the system [6]. Depletion was not considered for neutronics calculations since LMCR simulations were run at low power.

The solutions of the salt velocity field and the temperature profile of the system were achieved with Pronghorn by solving RANS equations through a standard k-epsilon approach [7]. A more detailed description of the methods incorporated for the solution of this equation can be found in reference [8].

The plating phenomenon was modeled using a 3×3 system of equations describing the concentrations of the chemical species of interest, in this case chromium, in three states: dissolved chromium in the molten salt (Cr_d), solid chromium suspended (colloid) in the salt (Cr_c), and solid chromium plated on the system surfaces (Cr_s).

The three equations in question are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial Cr_d}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (uCr_d) - \nabla \cdot \left[\left(D_{cr_d} + \frac{\nu_t}{Sc_t} \right) \nabla Cr_d \right] = -h^{d-s} (Cr_d - Cr_d^*) + h^{d-c} (Cr_c - Cr_s^*) \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial Cr_c}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (uCr_c) - \nabla \cdot \left[\left(D_{cr_c} + \frac{\nu_t}{Sc_t} \right) \nabla Cr_c \right] = -h^{d-c} (Cr_c - Cr_s^*) - h^{c-s} (Cr_c - 0) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial Cr_s}{\partial t} = +h^{d-s} (Cr_d - Cr_d^*) + h^{c-s} (Cr_c - 0) \quad (3)$$

Equation (1) describes the balance of dissolved chromium in the salt. The terms on the left-hand side represent the temporal variation, advection, and diffusion of the dissolved chromium concentration, respectively. On the right-hand side, there are two terms: the first accounts for the exchange between the dissolved chromium in the salt and the plated chromium on system surfaces, while the second represents the precipitation of dissolved chromium forming solid particles in suspension.

Equation (2) represents the balance of solid chromium in suspension (colloidal form). It has an analogous structure to Equation (1), but the right-hand side terms differ in meaning. The first term describes the exchange between dissolved and colloidal concentrations, while the second term corresponds to the mass transfer associated with colloids adhering to surfaces.

Finally, Equation (3) describes the temporal variation of solid chromium plated on the surfaces of the system. The terms on the right-hand side account for the exchanges between dissolved and plated chromium, and for the deposition of colloids, respectively. It is important to note that this equation does not include advection or diffusion terms, since it is assumed that once chromium adheres to a surface, it no longer migrates unless it dissolves back into the molten salt. The parameters u , D_{cr} , ν_t , and Sc_t appearing in the equations represent the velocity field, molecular diffusion coefficient, turbulent viscosity, and turbulent Schmidt number, respectively.

The factors h^{d-c} , h^{d-s} , and h^{c-s} are reaction rate coefficients that capture the kinetics of the exchange between the multiple states. Given the absence of reported values in literature, the coefficients were determined based on reasonable expected behavior of the system. The equilibrium values Cr_d^* and Cr_s^* define the maximum permissible concentrations of the dissolved, colloid, and solid species. To obtain these equilibrium values, the Thermochemica code was incorporated, which determines them by solving a minimization problem that reduces the global Gibbs free energy of the system [9].

The governing equation used for establishing the thermochemical equilibrium values is a dimensionless Gibbs free energy equation given by:

$$\frac{G}{RT} = \sum_{\lambda=1}^{\Lambda} n_{\lambda} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\lambda}} \chi_{i(\lambda)} \tilde{\mu}_i + \sum_{\omega=1}^{\Omega} n_{\omega} \tilde{\mu}_{\omega} \quad (4)$$

In equation (4), G is the total Gibbs energy of the multicomponent, multiphase system, R is the ideal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature. The first summation term accounts for the contributions to the Gibbs free energy from all the solution phases in the system, considering the mole fractions and chemical potentials of each constituent within those phases. The second summation term represents the contributions to the Gibbs free energy from the pure condensed phases. Together, these two terms define the total Gibbs free energy of the multicomponent system, which Thermochemica minimizes to determine the equilibrium state.

The variable n_{λ} denotes the number of moles of solution phase λ , and N_{λ} is the number of constituents present in that phase. Similarly, n_{ω} represents the number of moles of a pure condensed phase ω . The symbols Λ and Ω correspond to the total number of solutions and condensed phases, respectively. The quantity $\chi_{i(\lambda)}$ is the mole fraction of constituent i in solution phase λ and $\tilde{\mu}_i$ is its dimensionless chemical potential, while $\tilde{\mu}_{\omega}$ represents the dimensionless chemical potential of the pure condensed phase ω .

The dimensionless chemical potentials $\tilde{\mu}_i$ and $\tilde{\mu}_{\omega}$ come from the Molten Salt Thermal Properties Database Thermochemical (MSTDB-TC), which provides Gibbs energy models and values for molten salt components and related systems of interest with respect to molten salt reactor technology [10]. Thermochemica solver reaches a solution considering three important aspects of the thermodynamic equilibrium, which are: conservation of mass, Gibbs phase rule, and Gibbs energy of the system at a global minimum.

2.3. Multiphysics Scheme

Given the intrinsic coupling among the different physics involved, it is necessary to link the response of one code to the calculation performed by another. Based on this, a multiphysics hierarchy was established, allowing a continuous exchange of values among the different solvers to account for variations in external variables that affect the solution. This is one of the inherent advantages of using MOOSE-based applications [11].

The multiphysics coupling scheme is shown in Figure 2, where the information exchanges among the Griffin, Pronghorn, and Thermochemica codes can be identified during the computation of the simulation results.

Figure 2. Multiphysics coupling hierarchy

3. RESULTS

Power density and fission source terms were calculated for steady-state conditions at 25 kW thermal. Figure 3 shows the power density results obtained from the Griffin solver.

Figure 3. LMCR Power Density

The solutions of Pronghorn for the velocity fields and temperature profile are found in Figure 4.

Figure 4. LMCR Velocity & Temperature

A preliminary case was developed to study the dynamics and effects of the plating model. The case introduced 50 g of pure chromium dissolved in the salt, 1 g of solid chromium in suspension, and 1 g plated on the walls as initial conditions. Non-trivial concentrations of colloidal and solid chromium

were chosen to avoid numerical errors during the initial iteration. Additionally, the values of the constants h^{d-s} , h^{d-c} and h^{c-s} were set equal, with a value of $5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

The values of Cr_d^* and Cr_s^* obtained from Thermochemica were selected specifically for the element of interest. Cr_d^* was defined as the sum of equilibrium concentrations of $CrCl_2$ and $CrCl_3$, while Cr_s^* was the maximum allowable concentration of solid metallic chromium.

Diffusion and advection terms were neglected for this preliminary run. The simulated time was 10,000 seconds. A comparison of the initial and final values of concentration over the system can be seen in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 5. Initial concentrations of chromium: dissolved (left), colloid (center), solid plated (right)

Figure 6. Final concentrations of chromium: dissolved (left), colloid (center), solid plated (right)

It can be observed that, after performing the simulation, an exchange developed among the three states. Figure 7 shows the evolution of the different chromium states over time. Starting from initial values of 50 g, 1 g, and 1 g for dissolved chromium, colloidal chromium, and solid chromium, respectively, the results indicate final values of 4.58 g, 41.41 g, and 6.01 g. These results demonstrate a reasonable exchange among the three states; however, further testing and refinement of the model should be conducted in the future to confirm the validity of the results.

Figure 7. Evolution of chromium in LMCR for study case over 100000s (27.7h)

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained and the temporal evaluation of the plating phenomena allow identifying that the model describes the variation of the three variables of interest over time. Due to the strong temperature dependence of the equilibrium values computed by Thermochemica, and given the isothermal behavior of the LMCR, a homogeneous plating behavior is observed in the reactor. Therefore, it would be appropriate to evaluate this phenomenon in systems with stronger temperature gradients, where a non-homogeneous plating distribution can be observed (for instance, comparing the cold and hot legs of a reactor with a heat exchanger).

In the case of the LMCR, being a low-power model, the depletion steps are expected to be small enough that the accumulated fission products do not significantly alter the molten salt chemistry. Thus, this factor does not contribute substantially to the plating. However, when extending this work to higher power reactors, changes in the chemical potential and the presence of additional chemical species play an important role in determining the equilibrium values calculated by Thermochemica. Moreover, the reaction rate constants must be estimated experimentally, as they determine the rates of change. Nevertheless, the steady-state plating values are defined by the equilibrium values provided by Thermochemica.

Subsequent work should focus on the refinement and verification of the model. For validation purposes, the Molten Salt Test Loop Test Bed at INL should provide data to assess the model's accuracy and estimation of kinetic constants. Additionally, other species of interest, such as iron, nickel, and noble metals, should be tracked to study plating phenomena and the local deposition of heat sources.

Further work can also be carried out to incorporate uncertainties in thermophysical properties and evaluate their impact on the plating phenomenon. This includes assessing the phenomenon under different power levels and transient conditions, as well as incorporating depletion steps to study changes in salt chemistry due to the accumulation of fission products.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research made use of the resources of the High-Performance Computing Center at Idaho National Laboratory, which is supported by the Office of Nuclear Energy of the U.S. Department of Energy and the Nuclear Science User Facilities under Contract No. DE-AC07-05ID14517.

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